

THE NEW SPIRITUAL SPACE IS THE SPIRITUAL PERSON IMAGE-ENHANCING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. The article contains full comments related to the strategy of economic reforms in Uzbekistan and the process of its implementation. Aspects related to the impact of economic reforms on the spiritual image of a person are revealed.

Key words: Spirituality, reform, economic process, development, social processes, spiritual image, spiritual consciousness.

It is certainly possible to positively evaluate the changes that took place in the spiritual image of a person during the period of reforms. The spiritual world of people is becoming modern. It is also observed that some qualities have started to rise. At the same time, it is possible to see that some negative vices are preserved and new ones appear - these cases were explained in detail in the previous chapter. In order to protect the spiritual image of a person from their influence in the new socio-economic conditions, it will be necessary to create a completely new social environment corresponding to today's economic reality. A new spiritual space serves as such a social environment.

"What is the new spiritual space?" writes the President of the country.- In my opinion, it is an enlightened society that clearly reflects the spiritual image of the New Uzbekistan that we dream of, where our people aspire and where our country lives happily. The new spiritual space is characterized by:

ensuring personal freedom and moral security. A new spiritual space allows a person to think, work and live freely. In addition, he can protect the spiritual image of a person from various spiritual and ideological threats, spiritual decline and errors;

stability of the spiritual and spiritual environment that serves the spiritual development of a person. In the new spiritual space, people establish relations with each other based on the principles of humanity and mutual assistance;

the existence of a spiritual production process that encourages spiritual maturity. In the new spiritual space, social institutions based on humanitarian ideas and teachings are operating. They produce spiritual products that have a positive effect on the system of qualities and values of people;

abundance of spiritual products that ensure the spiritual maturity of a person. The new spiritual space will be rich in high spiritual products - original scientific treatises and works, novels and short stories, photos and films;

the formation of an educational system that introduces a person to humanitarian ideas and principles. The new spiritual space includes a system of different places that spread enlightenment to the members of the society.

Of course, the issue of establishing a new spiritual space is not a short-term goal. This area is of strategic importance and will be pursued for a long time. But there are not a few urgent, today's tasks related to its formation. These tasks are described in detail in the work of the head of state entitled "Strategy of New Uzbekistan". The current issue is related to the determination of measures and activities for the realization of these tasks on a general social scale.

"In the coming years," the President of Uzbekistan writes in his work, "it is appropriate to carry out the following tasks in order to raise the effectiveness of the work on forming a new spiritual space and the new thinking of our people to a high level and to further improve the system of activity in this regard"

First, "effective and systematic organization of the work of conveying to the general public the essence of the priority directions of the state policy and large-scale reforms in the field of spirituality and enlightenment". In the following years, the policy of the state in the field of spirituality and enlightenment became systematic and intensive. "On improving the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work and raising the development of the field to a new level", "On approving the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On measures to further increase the role and influence of culture and art in the life of society", "Education - on additional measures to further improve the education system The adoption of the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further develop the Uzbek language and improve the language policy in our country", and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop the concept of the development of the national idea at a new stage of Uzbekistan's development" indicates. Of course, the content and directions of the state policy in the field of spirituality and education are revealed to some extent in the events held in the places. However, as the head of state noted, these activities lack systematicity and efficiency. In our opinion, in order to ensure the systematicity of events, it is necessary to improve the methods of creating programs, to modernize the system of raising the capacity of organizers participating in the implementation of these programs.

Secondly, the systematic organization of activities aimed at studying and improving the socio-spiritual environment in the family, neighborhood,

educational institutions and labor teams, forming a map of the optimization of the socio-spiritual environment in the cross-section of regions based on the principle of "neighborhood-district-province-republic", modernizing this process wide introduction of information and communication technologies". It would be unfair to say that the specific aspects of the socio-spiritual environment in the above-mentioned subjects are always overlooked by sociologists. Of course, the "Social Opinion" republican public opinion research center, social science departments of local higher education institutions conducted sociological surveys on various aspects of the topic. In any case, the results of sociological research published in scientific and popular scientific journals in the country testify to this. It should also be noted that in recent years, the efforts of local authorities aimed at creating a healthy social and spiritual environment in families and neighborhoods have become more active. However, sociological surveys in this direction have not taken a systematic form, and the experience of conducting them regularly has not been established. These surveys are usually conducted on different topics and objectives, so they are not strictly related to each other. As a result, it is difficult to improve the dynamics of the socio-spiritual environment in the subjects. Secondly, there is no connection between the results of this sociological study and the efforts of local authorities to create a healthy social and spiritual environment in families and neighborhoods. In most cases, these efforts are not directed to eliminate the shortcomings and problems identified as a result of the sociological survey. The issues of improving the socio-spiritual environment in educational institutions and work communities are completely neglected. Taking this into account, it is necessary to carry out sociological surveys on the topic on the basis of the order of state bodies, to implement the practice of harmonizing decisions aimed at improving the socio-spiritual environment with the results of this survey.

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